

A Study Of Satisfaction With Remote Working Arrangements In Mumbai City

Aarti Sukheja

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: August 12, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: March 14, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Remote Work Arrangement, Job Satisfaction and Mumbai City.</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6350579</p>	<p><i>Dr. Remote working arrangements were rare a decade ago but with the advent of technology many businesses are now opting for remote teams. In fact, it's not uncommon if businesses permit employees to go for the remote working option almost completely. Remote work is a working style that allows employees to work from any place of their choice which is outside a conventional office environment. It is based on the concept that work can be done from anywhere and not just from a designated place. Development of digital technology is the trigger for this work arrangement. This arrangement gives flexibility to the employees to work outside of a traditional office environment. It allows both personal and professional life to coexist. Employers benefit from saving costs and higher productivity which is the outcome of a highly engaged workforce. It is increasingly popular trend, hence instead of resisting this trend, organizations should improve their remote work policies.</i></p> <p><i>The study is an attempt to investigate satisfaction of employees with remote working arrangements in Mumbai City.</i></p>

Introduction

Remote Working Arrangements are on a rise and is expected to increase its penetration significantly, given the current digital trigger in all the sectors. Working remotely which was unheard of is now catching up and becoming a mainstream option. Remote working arrangement allows professionals to work from home or any other place, avoids the need to commute and assures that personal life is not compromised. While employees have the flexibility to design their work days it also allows both professional and personal lives to coexist that maximises satisfaction. Employers benefit from a more engaged workforce and also save on costs. Against this backdrop, it is more important than ever that there is a paradigm shift in what society considers as a deemed fit place to work.

Decades ago, remote work did not exist as technology wasn't developed. But today modern technology enables us to do any job done from anywhere in the world. It has enabled us to coordinate with work teams at any time. Video Conferencing is valuable for boosting remote working arrangements. Live meetings permit teams to discuss and make important decisions from anywhere with a WIFI connection. This wouldn't have been possible in the past. Organisations are today thinking of remote working as a permanent option and have done away with their traditional offices, saving on costs. Remote working arrangements can make businesses thrive in pandemic in which employees can continue working from the safety of their homes and business can continue to grow.

Though many organisations have opted for this work arrangement many have also resisted this option fearing productivity issues. Employees may prefer remote working but companies may lack in policies to promote remote working. A good remote working policy can help companies save on costs and have an engaged work force.

The world is moving towards remote work and though this transition may pose challenges of managing a remote workforce but with the right strategies it can be a boon and a win-win for both companies and their employees. Majority of the employees are now looking for remote working opportunities. This increasingly popular trend is here to stay and companies are gearing up to upgrade their remote working policies and capabilities. They are creating performance parameters and making remote work teams accountable to achieve them.

The study is undertaken under the title: A Study of Job Satisfaction with Remote Working Arrangements in Mumbai City.

Review of Literature:

Susan Lund, Anu Madgavkar, James Manyika, and Sven Smit, Mc Kinsey & Company (2020) In this study activities and occupations are defined that can be done from home to better understand the future staying

power of remote work. It also throws light on issues surrounding remote work and how companies are now working on strategies to relieve them.

Karen Cygal, Matt Gilliland, Ed Hannibal, Emily Stirling, Deloitte (2021) The study highlights the growth of remote working arrangements and how it has become a catalyst for employers to become more innovative and accept the remote work arrangement which is now the new reality and will continue staying though in varying degrees.

Aline Holzwarth, Forbes (2021) The upsides and downsides of remote work have been discussed at length. The most popular reasons people prefer remote work are better work-life balance, increased productivity, less stress and avoiding a commute have been highlighted. The main downsides of remote work include isolation at work, lack of face-to-face contact, less knowledge-sharing and decreased team cohesion which has been brought out in this study.

ILO, Policy Brief (2020) Workingremotely is valuable for mitigating job losses, ensuring continuity and keeping population safe, has been brought out in the study. The objective of this brief is to estimate the potential share of workers who may perform in remote work arrangements and also discusses some of the policy issues associated with working from home.

Gartner Survey (2021) Gartner Survey reveals 50% of Indian hybrid workers consider themselves more productive when working remotely. Gartner Survey reveals that digital triggers, willingness to go for virtual meeting solutions, along with scheduled flexibility, have all promoted remotework arrangements. Indian workers, in this study, reported that they gained more productivity working remotely and not dealing with pronounced traffic conditions which could span three to four hours each way.

Research Gap: It can be observed that though many studies have been done on remote work but studies are needed to identify the satisfaction that employees get from remote working arrangements. This research is conducted to examine whether satisfaction is high or low from remote working arrangements in Mumbai city.

3. Relevance of the Study: The purpose of the study is to have an understanding of how remote work has had an impact on the satisfaction levels of employees who have opted for it. It can give valuable inputs to understand if remote working is just a stop gap arrangement or is here to stay. It also emphasizes the importance of the trend that emerged with the pandemic. It helped a great deal to understand the readiness of the people to come out of traditional office set ups and opt for remote work. This study intends to study the pros of remote work and also how most organisations are now taking this as a permanent option.

4. Scope of the Study:

4.1 Conceptual Scope: Two hundred employees (of which 100 males and 100 females), from a range of background, were interviewed. All the 200 employees were on remote working arrangements in Mumbai City only. This study focuses only on white collar employees only.

4.2 Geographical Scope: The study covers employees in remote working arrangements in Mumbai City only.

5. Methodology:

5.1 Class of respondent For the purpose of the survey total 200 employees who are in remote working in Mumbai City has been selected on random basis.

5.2 Sampling method Method of convenience sampling was adopted.

5.3 Method of data collection The research design of the study uses a mix of primary and secondary data.

5.3.1 Primary data will be obtained using a structured interview schedule, with some open-ended questions, to 200 employees in remote working arrangements.

5.3.2 Secondary data will be used to support the study collected from books, journals, websites, and newspapers.

5.4 Statistical Technique of analysis of data: Primary data collected was analysed using tabulation and percentage method

6. Objective of the Study:

1. To find out level of job satisfaction among white collar employees in remote working arrangements in Mumbai City.

7. Hypothesis of the Study:

Ho: There is low level of job satisfaction among white collar employees in remote working arrangements.

H1: There is high level of job satisfaction among white collar employees in remote working arrangements.

8. Result:

Table I: Distribution of employees on the basis of preference for remote working arrangements

Remote Work	Number	Percentage
Will take up the offer immediately	130	65%
Will compare and decide	30	15%
No preference	05	2.5%
Will continue in traditional office arrangement	35	17.5%
Total	200	100%

Source: Derived from questionnaire

Source: Derived from Table 1

Explanation of Table 1 and Graph 1

The preference for remote work among the respondents is observed to be high. 65% of respondents said that they will immediately accept a remote working arrangements offered to them. 30% said that they decide after comparing benefits. 35% of the respondents said that they would continue in traditional office set ups.

Table 2: Distribution of respondents by advantages with remote working arrangements:

Advantages of remote working	Number	Percentage
Flexibility of schedule	150	75%
No need to commute	136	68%
Saving Money	130	65%
Better Health	150	75%
Work Life Balance	145	72.5%
Pursue Hobbies	135	67.5%
Reduced Leaves	140	70%
Timeliness	140	70%

Source: Derived from questionnaire

Graph 2: Distribution of respondents by advantages with remote working arrangements:

Source: Derived from Table 2

Explanation of Table 2 and Graph 2

Table 2 and Graph 2 highlights the advantages enjoyed by employees in remote working arrangements. The most obvious reason why people want to work remotely is because it offers them a more flexible lifestyle. They can pursue higher education qualifications or pick up a new skill. Work Life balance ranks second when it comes to satisfaction with remote working arrangements. Employees get more freedom and can attend to their personal issues too as and when needed. Employees can do things as per their convenience, like picking kids from a school or even going for a doctor's appointment. There is no need to commute, which helps to save money. Better health, timeliness, reduced leaves are some other benefits of remote working arrangements which enhances the job satisfaction of the respondents in the study.

9. Conclusion of the study:

Remote working has all kinds of benefits including higher motivation levels amongst employees, enhanced productivity, and improved employee retention. Very recently, remote working has become a way of life for most employees. It can be safely said that the pandemic has made this a 'new normal' for many employees. It was the pandemic that motivated companies to try remote working as a survival measure. Subsequently a host of other benefits and given the cost saving advantage, companies now want to have it on a permanent basis. Though some argue that homes might not be an ideal space to work, and may lack in infrastructure with varied distractions, many argue that remote working has many advantages. Organisations across the world are now considering remote working as a permanent arrangement. It makes sense both to make financial savings and increase productivity. Significant savings in cost from reduced office space, travel and infrastructure costs reveal why organisations are lured to this arrangement.

While remote work has its flipside but it will give employees more time with family, commuting time and cost will be saved and there will be enhanced flexibility to balance work and life. Working in remote arrangements can also aid learning new skills. Findings confirm that remote working becomes the norm geographical limitations will disappear promoting labour mobility of the next level.

From the above table and graph it is concluded that level of job satisfaction is high among white collar employees in remote working arrangements in Mumbai City. Hence, we reject the null hypothesis and accept alternate hypothesis.

11. Limitation of the study:

1. The sample consists of only 200 employees.
2. The sample consists of only white-collar employees.
3. The sample consists of employees only from Mumbai City.

References

- Adams-Prassl, A., T. Boneva, M. Golin, and C. Rauh (2020): “Work tasks that can be done from home: Evidence on variation within & across occupations and industries,” CEPR Discussion Paper No. DP14901. Available at: [Work Tasks That Can Be Done From Home: Evidence on Variation Within and Across Occupations and Industries \(repec.org\)](https://www.repec.org/papers/cepr/2020/013)
- Dev, S. M., & Sengupta, R. (2020). Covid-19: Impact on the Indian economy. IGIDR Working Paper, WP-2020-013, Available at: [WP-2020-013.pdf \(igidr.ac.in\)](https://www.igidr.ac.in/pdf/publication/WP-2020-013.pdf)
- Dingel, J. I., & Neiman, B. (2020). How Many Jobs Can be Done at Home? Becker Friedman Institute. White paper, pp. 2-6, Available at: [How Many Jobs Can be Done at Home? \(nber.org\)](https://www.nber.org/papers/w26152)
- Allen, T. D., Golden, T. D. and Shockley, K. M. (2015) ‘How Effective Is Telecommuting? Assessing the Status of Our Scientific Findings’, *Psychological Science in the Public Interest*, 16(2), pp. 40–68.
- Hall, N., 2018. The impact of remote social work field placements on academic performance. *Advances in Social Work and Welfare Education*, 20(1), p.185.
- Clancy, M. (2020), “The Case for Remote Work”, *Economics Working Papers*, No. 20007, Iowa State University, Available at: Economics, https://lib.dr.iastate.edu/econ_workingpapers/102
- Dockery, A. M. and Bawa, S. (2017) ‘When two worlds collude: Working from home and family functioning’, *International Labour Review*, Available at : [When two worlds collude: Working from home and family functioning in Australia - DOCKERY - 2018 - International Labour Review - Wiley Online Library](https://www.birmingham.ac.uk/Documents/college-social-sciences/business/research/wirc/epp-working-from-home-COVID-19-lockdown.pdf)
<https://www.birmingham.ac.uk/Documents/college-social-sciences/business/research/wirc/epp-working-from-home-COVID-19-lockdown.pdf>
<http://www.igidr.ac.in/pdf/publication/WP-2020-022.pdf>

Author Information

Dr. Aarti Sukheja

Associate Professor in Economics,
Pillai College of Arts, Commerce and Science
(Autonomous),
New Panvel, Maharashtra, India
